

Scientometric Study of Corporate Communication Research in G20 Countries

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the research productivity in Corporate Communication among G20 countries. The dataset utilized spans from 1999 to 2022, sourced from the Scopus database. Employing scientometric techniques, the research investigates various aspects of research productivity, including impact, collaboration levels, and keywords, offering a comprehensive overview of publications in this field since the inception of G20 countries' collaboration. The highest Annual Growth Rate (AGR) was observed in 2004 (130.77), followed by 2000 (84.62) and 2008 (80). Despite a dip in 2020 (-15.38), there was a positive AGR in publications during the pandemic. This study holds particular significance and timeliness as India assumes the presidency for G20, marking a quarter century of G20 collaboration. The study's findings suggest a positive correlation between authors' and journals' h and g indexes, indicating a linear relationship. While the United States boasts the highest number of published documents (n=323), Russia received the most citations (n=2297), highlighting disparities in publication output and impact. The research also outlines future projections, study limitations, and implications. Analyzing trends, impact, collaboration, and emerging topics informs strategic decision-making, policy formulation, and resource allocation, pushing the boundaries of current knowledge and revealing potential avenues for exploration.

Keywords: Corporate Communication, G20 countries, Scopus, Time Series Analysis, VOSViewer

Introduction

The Group of 20 Nations is a platform for global-level cooperation for economic growth and has a pertinent role in enabling governance mechanisms and structures for a forward-looking economic role, held in India from 1st December 2022 to 30th November 2023. Its inception can be traced to 1999, after the Asian financial crisis. It initially emphasised macro-economic aspects but has evolved to encompass issues that impact the lives of people in the countries. Currently, the “G20 group includes 19 countries and 1 European Union-Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, Mexico, Republic of Korea, Russia, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Türkiye, United Kingdom, United States of America” (Agarwal & Whalley, 2020). Collectively this behemoth “represent 85% of the global GDP; 75% of global trade and two-thirds of the world population” (National Portal of India, 2022). The EU countries are, “Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Republic of

Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden” (Mathur & Agarwal, 2021).

Scientometric research is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on the quantitative analysis of research publications, their authors, institutions, or countries involved. By utilizing scientometric techniques, researchers explore in order to enhance their insights into the knowledge structures and dynamics of scientific fields, identifying research trends and advancements, and assessing institutional productivity. Furthermore, scientometric research plays a pertinent role in evaluating the impact and influence of scientific work. By examining publication output, citation analysis, collaboration networks, and other bibliometric indicators, scientometric research provides valuable insights into the community's productivity and influence. This information can be used to assess the growth

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and evolution of research fields, identify emerging trends, and evaluate the impact created by researchers or institutions.

Research publications focused on the G20 countries provide valuable insights into their performance, initiatives, and impacts on global markets. The research publications from the G20 countries are important resources for policymakers, economists, and business leaders who seek to understand the trends and implications of research by G20 countries.

The outcomes of the study will be valuable points for information gathering for organisations, library professionals, academicians, and research institutions, as the study delves into mapping networks, gauging trends, and predicting research output. The research community of Corporate Communication, Public Relations, G20 countries, and Management Sciences will be able to find information about productivity and the impact of research in this field. The assessment will also set grounds for monitoring research through metrics that examine the impact and analyse performance through the g-index, h-index and their relationship.

Literature review

Cornelisson (2023) looks at the field of Corporate Communication as an enabler of integrating “internal and external communication with the overall purpose of establishing and maintaining favourable reputations” amongst organisations. The concept has been researched from different perspectives based on its aspects and utilities (Belasen & Belasen, 2018; Bharthur, 2021; Kolahgar *et al.*, 2021). However, there is a paucity of literature on scientometric assessment of corporate communication publications, especially for a specified set of countries.

The field of scientometrics contributes to the advancement of scientific knowledge as an information-driven process. It encompasses various methods to assess research quality, impact, citation patterns, scientific field mapping, and utilise metrics in research-oriented policy and management. It offers several benefits, providing a comprehensive understanding of the subject (Garg *et al.*, 2020; Gaggero *et al.*, 2020; Pasko *et al.*, 2022).

Katz *et al.* (2006) examined how a desktop scientometric environment can be utilised to provide convenient public access to bibliometric information and charted the possibilities for research assessment. However, during the process of investigation, it does not take into account the dynamic nature of the ever-changing interdisciplinary interactions. Verk *et al.* (2019) tries to fill in the void by discussing the evolving aspects of corporate communication

literature. The highly competitive environment and the total use of bibliometric approaches and assessment of science have led to the adoption of assessment methods for publication trends and practices. Taking a leaf from previous research and acknowledging the knowledge networks, Ji *et al.* (2020) looked at the authorship patterns and citation networks emerging in the communication landscape. This gives a comprehensive outlook towards approaching the research questions and aims. With the use of mapping techniques for research, the ecosystem of literature can be investigated and visualised.

Al-Khoury *et al.* (2022) analysed intellectual capital from the Scopus database, exploring a 64-year sample of publications that would throw light on future possibilities. Lim *et al.* (2023) conducted a scientometric and bibliometric analysis of the literature on developmental disabilities in Africa. Sun *et al.* (2023) used metrics to gauge scientific output from various countries in the field of cancer research and investigated the status and future trends. Scientometric and bibliometric analysis of any field presents fertile ground for further research and policy-making (Murugan *et al.*, 2022; Rejeb *et al.*, 2022; Zhang & Lin, 2022; Zhu *et al.*, 2022).

This approach allows researchers to create visual representations of the connections between different publications, reducing the challenges of analyzing vast datasets (Vijayakumar & Choi, 2022). It enables researchers to quantitatively interpret the historical and current state of specific areas of study.

Scope of the study

This systematic study encompassed formulating research design and objectives that become the basis for answering the research question. Data was mined from Scopus, a widely recognized abstract and citation database. It provides a comprehensive platform for accessing scientific literature and analyzing research trends. Past studies have not explored into the scientometric assessment of corporate communication research, that too in G20 countries and for the period beginning from G20's inception year, 1999. The present study looks at 1063 publications to gauge the scholarship of research. Amongst the G20 countries, Estonia and Luxembourg were excluded because there weren't any publications indexed from these countries. The temporal distribution of the study is 1999-2022, and only research articles published in the English language have been included for the study, owing to its universality and high number of publications.

Objectives

1. To highlight top journals of G20 countries

publishing in the field of Corporate Communication during 1999-2022.

2. To find out documents cited by authors and identify the top authors in G20 countries in the field of Corporate Communication during 1999-2022.
3. To analyse trends of growth of publications of Corporate Communication during 1999-2022 for G20 countries.
4. To calculate Annual Growth Rate, Annual Ratio of Growth, Relative Growth Rate, and Doubling Time of Corporate Communication publications during 1999-2022 for G20 countries.
5. To evaluate the degree of collaboration of authors of Corporate Communication during 1999-2022 for G20 countries.
6. To analyse G20 countries publishing research and their scientific production index in the field of Corporate Communication during 1999-2022.
7. To predict future production levels of Corporate Communication publications by G20 countries.

Hypothesis (H)

- H-I H_{a0} - There is no significant correlation between the h and g indexes of authors
- HH_{a1} - There is a significant correlation between the h and g indexes of authors
- H-II H_{b0} - There is no significant correlation between the h and g indexes of journals
- H_{b1} - There is a significant correlation between the h and g indexes of journals

Methodology

During the examination of Corporate Communication publications, we inserted the research string “(TITLE-ABS-KEY (“corporate communication”*) AND PUBYEAR > 1998 AND PUBYEAR <2023) AND (LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “United States”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, “United Kingdom”) OR.....LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, “Latvia”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, “ar”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, “English”))”. The initial query resulted in 2062 documents, which were then restricted to G20 countries, resulting in 1700 publications that were suitable for the study. Results were refined further, to include only English language articles, enabling a corpus of 1063 documents. This commenced the procedure for analysing journals, authors, trends, collaborations, AGR, ARoG, Relative Growth Rate and Doubling Time of publications, Scientific Production Index, and predicting global research output levels. The information was exported as a CSV file. The procedure for collection, elimination and analysis of the data is condensed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Inquiry Steps Matrix

The visualisation for understanding the scientific landscapes of 1063 publications was accomplished through VOSViewer. The VOSViewer creates a platform for network, density, cluster, and occurrence visualisation for analysing bibliometric and scientometric networks. It provides techniques to analyse structures and relationships within the data (Van Eck & Waltman, 2009). Figure 2 displays the upward trajectory and expansion of publications over the temporal distribution, providing insights into the output of publications and research interest trends.

Data analysis

Publication trends

Figure 2. Publication frequency and cumulative index in Corporate Communication research in G20 countries (1999-2022)

It can be fathomed from Figure 2 that the frequency of publication during 2001-2003 was not so much as during other periods. Post the initial dip, the subsequent years witnessed a gradual rise in the number of publications. The production reached its acme in 2022, positing an increasing trend for research in the field of corporate communication from 2020 onwards. The number of publications during the period of the COVID pandemic dipped from previous years, exhibiting a shift in research interests during the affected period and resumption as the pandemic waned. Years 2018 and 2019 had almost similar levels of production, while years

2005 and 2007 had matching levels of publications. This enabled them to track research and arrive at a quantitative measure for performance evaluation and benchmarking. This also showcased the reduced output years that may be influenced by fluctuations like funding availability, collaborations, or shifts in research priorities. The cumulative accruing plot also provides a dynamic view of the research landscape, signaling the ebb and flow of research activity.

Price's theory (Price, 2011) also postulated that a rise in publication facilitates growth of knowledge, where growth refers to enhancement in actual size, a change of state, and development of literature. It can be applied to trace the evolution of science and present the patterns that hold true with a high degree of accuracy over time. These results can be helpful in future planning and resource allocation.

Countries publishing research

The 1063 documents have originated from the G20 countries, and 34 countries have published three or more documents, while the remaining 12 countries have fewer publications. The research output is led by the United States and the United

Kingdom contributing 46% of global research publication output, highlighting the critical efforts in the development and furtherance of corporate communication studies. Out of these, 13 countries could encourage only a single digit number of publications over the span of two decades. It can also be deduced that countries having nominal GDP rank 48 or lesser make a place in the top 10 countries (Table 1). The country ranked tenth in the list has maintained an average citation score of 61.06, the highest in the top 10 countries with maximum research production output. Barring this outlier, it can be reasoned that economically developed countries with higher GDP ranks, have fared better in research on corporate communication. USA acquires the maximum percentage share of G20 countries' output. It tops the chart of the Scientific Production Index (Number of documents per country/total number of records of G20 countries*100) with a score of 30.39, followed by the UK at 16.09 and Spain at 7.06. The host G20 country for 2023, India makes its place in the Top 10 countries with 35 documents, 105 citations, and a 3.29 scientific production index.

Table 1. This is the list of G20 countries that published three or more documents in the field of Corporate Communication. *Source - As per World Economic Outlook Database April 2023

S. No.	Countries	Quantity	Citation	Avg. Citation per document	Nominal GDP Rank	Scientific Production Index
1	United States	323	484	1.50	1	30.39
2	United Kingdom	171	30	0.18	6	16.09
3	Spain	75	444	5.92	15	7.06
4	Germany	63	908	14.41	4	5.93
5	Italy	63	204	3.24	8	5.93
6	Australia	59	2308	39.12	13	5.55
7	Denmark	58	12	0.21	38	5.46
8	Canada	37	527	14.24	9	3.48
9	India	35	105	3.00	5	3.29
10	Finland	34	2076	61.06	48	3.20
11	Sweden	34	34	1.00	25	3.20
12	South Africa	32	269	8.41	39	3.01
13	France	27	1173	43.44	7	2.54
14	China	24	304	12.67	2	2.26
15	Belgium	16	374	23.38	24	1.51
16	South Korea	16	38	2.38	12	1.51
17	Brazil	13	204	15.69	10	1.22
18	Indonesia	13	12	0.92	16	1.22
19	Portugal	13	54	4.15	51	1.22

S. No.	Countries	Quantity	Citation	Avg. Citation per document	Nominal GDP Rank	Scientific Production Index
20	Austria	11	171	15.55	31	1.03
21	Slovenia	11	42	3.82	88	1.03
22	Türkiye	9	221	24.56	19	0.85
23	Poland	6	18	3.00	22	0.56
24	Russian Federation	6	2297	382.83	11	0.56
25	Romania	5	191	38.20	45	0.47
26	Czech Republic	4	31	7.75	47	0.38
27	Hungary	4	24	6.00	57	0.38
28	Ireland	4	298	74.50	26	0.38
29	Japan	4	51	12.75	3	0.38
30	Slovakia	4	582	145.50	62	0.38
31	Taiwan	4	27	6.75	21	0.38
32	Cyprus	3	148	49.33	108	0.28
33	Greece	3	1438	479.33	54	0.28
34	Malta	3	934	311.33	129	0.28

Top Authors

Authors publishing three or more documents are mentioned in Table 2. It is interesting to note that Dolphin R.R. has a maximum number of documents yet has an average citation score of 19.67, while Arvidsson S. with only three documents has an average citation score of 71.67 (highest) in the field of Corporate Communication. It is also evident that out of the top 10 authors, 9 have published an equal number of documents each, yet they differ significantly in terms of the citations, signaling towards their research quality levels.

Gupta S. has an overall g-index of 33, followed by Capriotti P. and Meng J. with a g-index of 22. Few authors, despite high frequencies of citations, have

Figure 3. G20 countries that published three or more documents in field of Corporate Communication

Table 2. Top 10 authors publishing three or more documents

S. No.	Author	Author ID	Documents (1999-2022)	Citations (1999-2022)	Avg. Citations	H-index (Overall)	G-Index (Overall)
1	Dolphin R.R.	7004678464	6	118	19.67	7	8
2	Arvidsson S.	35758579700	3	215	71.67	5	11
3	Blombäck A.	22033248800	3	170	56.67	7	7
4	Brunninge O.	19638696400	3	170	56.67	5	8
5	Goodman M.B.	8653622800	3	67	22.33	8	9
6	Macnamara J.	36053138900	3	61	20.33	18	23
7	Capriotti P.	18433333100	3	38	12.67	11	22
8	Meng J.	55179310800	3	30	10.00	10	22
9	Gupta S.	55495191500	3	25	8.33	18	33
10	Hutt R.W.	36023765300	3	16	5.33	3	6

Figure 4. Scatter plot of h and g index for top authors in Corporate Communication

lesser impact as per h and g indexes. Arvidsson S. has a 5 and 11 overall h and g index respectively while Gupta S. has the highest h and g index despite average citations of 8.33. Figure 4 evinces authors' h and g index represented through a scatter plot. The h-g scatter plot showcases the linear relationship between the indexes of authors with a positive correlation ($r^2=0.796\approx 1$). The equation $y=mx+c$ ($1.5977x+0.2011$) is satisfied by the variables.

Top journals

As seen in Table 3, there are ten top journals in corporate communication during the period under study from the G20 countries with 10 or more

publications. It shows that journals having a high number of publications do not have high levels of impact. The “Corporate Communications” journal with the highest number of publications (163) has a lower cite score than the “Journal of Business Ethics” (cite score 12), having only 12 documents. Out of the top 10 journals, four have been published by Emerald Group Holdings Ltd. Figure 5 shows a linear and positive relation of the h and g indexes. It indicates that the values, indeed, are directly proportional and an increase in the h-index translates to a rise in the g-index as well. The value of r^2 is 0.893 (≈ 1) and $y=0.9674x+32.956$, which reflects the fitness of actual data to scatter plot line values.

Figure 5. Scatter plot of h and g index for top journals in Corporate Communication

Table 3. Top 10 journals publishing ten or more documents

S. No.	Name of Journal	Publications	Cite Score 2022	Publisher	H-Index (Overall)	G-index (Overall)
1	“Corporate Communications”	163	3.7	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	71	105
2	“Journal of Communication Management”	74	4.5	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	47	73
3	“Corporate Communications: An International Journal”	51	3	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	47	75
4	“Public Relations Review”	44	7.4	Elsevier	104	160
5	“Corporate Reputation Review”	23	3	Palgrave Macmillan Ltd.	71	117
6	“European Journal of Marketing”	18	8.1	Emerald Group Holdings Ltd.	162	200
7	“Journal of Marketing Communications”	14	6.7	Routledge	59	93
8	“International Journal of Business Communication”	12	5.8	SAGE Publications Ltd	27	36
9	“Journal of Business Ethics”	12	12	Springer	200	200
10	“Communicatio”	11	0.8	Routledge	17	32

Top cited documents

The document published by the group “Wagner T.; Lutz R.J.; Weitz B.A.” (n=700) received the highest citations followed by groups of “Tate W.L.; Ellram L.M.; Kirchoff J.F.” (n=486) and “Bundy J.; Pfarrer M.D.; Short C.E.; Coombs W.T.” (n=467). Among the list of top documents cited at least 200 times, only two documents were single-authored out of 17 documents, belonging to Aula, P. (n=241) and Ford, J.D. (n=201). This shows that multi-authored documents have been cited more as compared to single-authored documents, signaling that multi-authored papers of corporate communication have better quality or citation potential than single author documents.

Annual Growth Rate (AGR), ARoG, RGR and Dt

The annual growth rate of publications has been calculated for 1999-2022 using Grácio *et al.* (2012) formula. The publication levels witnessed a dipping trajectory intermittently and a high path in 2021 and 2022, gesticulating a positive outlook for future years. The highest AGR was in 2004 (130.77), followed by 2000 (84.62) and 2008 (80). Post the dip in 2020 (-15.38), the publications had a positive AGR during the pandemic period.

By analyzing the annual ratio of growth in

scientific outputs, we present quantitative evidence of the rate at which scientific knowledge is expanding in the corporate communication discipline in G20 countries. Mahapatra’s Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (Dt.) model have been used to gauge growth rate (Mahapatra, 1985). It’s an effective method to have an assessment of publications (Verma & Shukla, 2019). Table 5 and Figure 6 showcase the RGR and Dt. of publications from 1999-2022. Interestingly, we see a dip in doubling time in the year 2022, which cues an apparent decrease in the coming years. Years 2020 and 2021 had a similar doubling time of 11.55 that rose from 8.66 in 2019 and had a similar level in 2022. The Annual Ratio of Growth (ARoG) had a fluctuating trajectory. The ARoG values have been rising since the pandemic years.

Figure 7 showcases the positive and negative values of AGR accumulated over the years. We can see that mostly there has been a large positive growth and lesser declines in AGRs of the publications. The water flow chart gives us a metaphorical visualisation symbolising flow of publications with the varied intensity of flow each year. Higher columns indicate periods of significant growth and lower columns represent slower growth.

Table 4. Top documents cited for at least 200 times

Id	Documents	Citations	Doi
1	“Wagner T.; Lutz R.J.; Weitz B.A.”	700	10.1509/jmkg.73.6.77
2	“Tate W.L.; Ellram L.M.; Kirchoff J.F.”	486	10.1111/j.1745-493X.2009.03184.x
3	“Bundy J.; Pfarrer M.D.; Short C.E.; Coombs W.T.”	467	10.1177/0149206316680030
4	“Parguel B.; Benoît-moreau F.; Larceneux F.”	390	10.1007/s10551-011-0901-2
5	“Adams C.A.; Mcnicholas P.”	338	10.1108/09513570710748553
6	“Groza M.D.; Pronschinske M.R.; Walker M.”	322	10.1007/s10551-011-0834-9
7	“Branco M.C.; Rodrigues L.L.”	294	10.1108/13563280610680821
8	“Morsing M.; Schultz M.; Nielsen K.U.”	269	10.1080/13527260701856608
9	“Smith M.; Taffler R.J.”	269	10.1108/09513570010353738
10	“Barako D.G.; Brown A.M.”	263	10.1007/s10997-008-9053-x
11	“Welch M.; Jackson P.R.”	257	10.1108/13563280710744847
12	“Aula P.”	241	10.1108/10878571011088069
13	“Goodman M.B.; Booth N.; Matic J.A.”	220	10.1108/13563281111156853
14	“Luo Y.; Shenkar O.”	214	10.1057/palgrave.jibs.8400197
15	“Argenti P.A.; Druckenmiller B.”	205	10.1057/palgrave.crr.1540005
16	“Hutton J.G.; Goodman M.B.; Alexander J.B.; Genest C.M.”	203	10.1016/S0363-8111(01)00085-6
17	“Ford J.D.”	201	10.1108/09534819910300855

Table 5. Annual Ratio of Growth, AGR, RGR and Dt.

Year	Documents	ARoG	AGR	Aggregate Publications	w-1	w-2	Relative Growth Rate	Doubling Time
1999	13	0	0	13	-	2.56	0	0
2000	24	1.85	84.62	84.62	2.56	3.61	1.05	0.66
2001	14	0.58	-41.67	42.95	3.61	3.93	0.32	2.17
2002	12	0.86	-14.29	28.66	3.93	4.14	0.21	3.30
2003	13	1.08	8.33	37.00	4.14	4.33	0.19	3.65
2004	30	2.31	130.77	167.77	4.33	4.66	0.33	2.10
2005	25	0.83	-16.67	151.10	4.66	4.87	0.21	3.30
2006	33	1.32	32.00	183.10	4.87	5.09	0.22	3.15
2007	25	0.76	-24.24	158.86	5.09	5.24	0.15	4.62
2008	45	1.80	80.00	238.86	5.24	5.45	0.21	3.30
2009	40	0.89	-11.11	227.75	5.45	5.61	0.16	4.33
2010	57	1.43	42.50	270.25	5.61	5.80	0.19	3.65
2011	44	0.77	-22.81	247.44	5.80	5.92	0.12	5.78
2012	50	1.14	13.64	261.07	5.92	6.05	0.13	5.33
2013	60	1.20	20.00	281.07	6.05	6.18	0.13	5.33
2014	58	0.97	-3.33	277.74	6.18	6.29	0.11	6.30
2015	67	1.16	15.52	293.26	6.29	6.41	0.12	5.78
2016	56	0.84	-16.42	276.84	6.41	6.50	0.09	7.70
2017	70	1.25	25.00	301.84	6.50	6.60	0.10	6.93
2018	66	0.94	-5.71	296.13	6.60	6.68	0.08	8.66
2019	65	0.98	-1.52	294.61	6.68	6.76	0.08	8.66
2020	55	0.85	-15.38	279.23	6.76	6.82	0.06	11.55
2021	59	1.07	7.27	286.50	6.82	6.88	0.06	11.55
2022	82	1.39	38.98	325.48	6.88	6.96	0.08	8.66

Figure 6. RGR and Dt. of Corporate Communication publications

Degree of collaboration (DoC)

We investigated the DoC in the field of corporate communication utilising the formula by Subramanyam (1983), which is calculated through a ratio of uni/multi-authored documents and total documents. Table 6 highlights the degree variance from 0.38 to 0.12 throughout the temporal distribution, showing that there has been a decrease

Figure 7. Waterflow analysis of AGR of publications

in single-author documents and an increase in multiple-author documents. The year 2003 had the highest DC of 0.62 while the maximum number of multi-authored documents was 72 in 2022.

Table 7. Hypothesis Testing

Category	Correlation Coeff. (R)	Degrees of Freedom (dF)	Covariance	Statistic	p-value	Significance
Authors	0.8924	8	43.2444	5.5921	0.0005149	Significant
Journals	0.9449	12	3643.7582	10.0038	3.56676×10 ⁻⁷	Significant

scores go along with soaring Y variable scores. The coefficient of determination comes to 0.7964, and the p-value is .0005149. The result is significant at $p < .05$. Since the p -value $< \alpha$, H_0 is rejected. The population's correlation is considered to be not equal to the expected correlation. The difference between the sample correlation and the expected correlation

is big enough to be statistically significant.

The value of R is 0.9449 for the Journal category. The value of the coefficient of determination is 0.8928, and the p-value is $< .00001$. The result is significant at $p < .05$. The null hypothesis that the h-index and g-index are independent is rejected at the 5 percent level based on the Pearson Correlation test.

Table 8. Time Series Analysis - Global Corporate Communication Research Output Prediction

S.No.	Year	x	Y	X	XY	X ²
1	1999	0	13	-11.5	-149.5	132.25
2	2000	1	24	-10.5	-252	110.25
3	2001	2	14	-9.5	-133	90.25
4	2002	3	12	-8.5	-102	72.25
5	2003	4	13	-7.5	-97.5	56.25
6	2004	5	30	-6.5	-195	42.25
7	2005	6	25	-5.5	-137.5	30.25
8	2006	7	33	-4.5	-148.5	20.25
9	2007	8	25	-3.5	-87.5	12.25
10	2008	9	45	-2.5	-112.5	6.25
11	2009	10	40	-1.5	-60	2.25
12	2010	11	57	-0.5	-28.5	0.25
13	2011	12	44	0.5	22	0.25
14	2012	13	50	1.5	75	2.25
15	2013	14	60	2.5	150	6.25
16	2014	15	58	3.5	203	12.25
17	2015	16	67	4.5	301.5	20.25
18	2016	17	56	5.5	308	30.25
19	2017	18	70	6.5	455	42.25
20	2018	19	66	7.5	495	56.25
21	2019	20	65	8.5	552.5	72.25
22	2020	21	55	9.5	522.5	90.25
23	2021	22	59	10.5	619.5	110.25
24	2022	23	82	11.5	943	132.25
Total		276	1063		3143.5	1150
$a = \Sigma Y/N$			44.29			
$b = \Sigma XY/\Sigma X^2$			2.73			
Prediction						
1	2028			90.76		
2	2030			96.23		
3	2040			123.56		
4	2050			150.90		

Future projections

Time Series Analysis was utilised to estimate the future of Corporate Communication publications. Taking base year as the middle value (2011) of our data set of 24 years, we predict that the number of publications from the G20 countries in Corporate Communication will grow in the upcoming years. Going by the trends and estimating as per the formula, “Year ‘ $a = \Sigma Y/N$ ’ + (Year ‘ $b = \Sigma XY / \Sigma X^2 \times (2028 - 2011)$),” we can estimate that there will be 91 publications in 2028, 96 publications in 2030, 124 publications in 2040 and 151 publications in 2050.

Discussion

This study gives us an insight into the implications and potential of corporate communication research coming from G20 countries. Firstly, the study puts forward a benchmarking and comparison of research output and the impact of corporate communication publications, creating grounds for understanding the contributions to variations in productivity and influence across the nations. Secondly, we could see interdisciplinary collaborations with about 46% pertaining to Business Management and Accounting, 25% to Social Sciences, 8% to Economics, 5% to Arts and Humanities, and remaining in other fields. The results from various scientometric analyses show that the domain of corporate communication research has an upward trajectory of publications. For example, there were only 13 publications in 1999 (Figure 2) and 82 articles in 2022. Relatively, there has been an increase in publications in 2022, reaching its peak, indicating enhanced research activity. With the pandemic setting in, the amount of publications were affected which could be due to shift in research interests. There was a stable research output during 2018 and 2019. The years 2005 and 2007 had comparable levels of publication, thereby mirroring a consistent research activity. These variations could be due to various factors impacting research productivity.

The Scientific Production Index was maximum for the United States, owing to its high quantity of publications as compared to other countries. However, despite the *numero uno* position in publication output, it lags behind Russia, which has 2297 citations, and Finland, which received 2076 citations. The quality of research publications is not dependent on the number of publications, as countries with lower quantities of publications had higher average citation per document scores. The authors who published three or more documents were few, and Arvidsson S. had the maximum citations for his publications. The h-index of authors

highlighted their research impact, and it was seen that Macnamara, J. and Gupta, S. emerged as authors with high levels of influence and recognition within the researchers’ community. However, it could also be influenced by factors like citation practices of the corporate communication field, career lengths of the authors, and variation in citation patterns. Therefore, we utilised other parameters to get a comprehensive outlook to understand the author’s research impact. We confirm the results by using the g-index and measuring the highest number of publications (n) that received at least (n^2) citations.

The “Corporate Communications” journal is the most sought-after journal (with maximum publications) amongst list of top 10 journals that have published ten or more documents during 1999–2022. Amongst the top cited documents (cited more than 200 times), there were only two single-authored documents that received 241 and 201 citations. The rest 15 documents were multi-authored. Through the water flow analysis, we could see a stubby flow of publications in the initial years. The volume of publications in the past five years showcases a developing research landscape and growing interest in Corporate Communication studies. A significant surge in research productivity was witnessed in 2022. However, the flow of publications is not uniform throughout the time frame. The irregular patterns of flow of publications could be marred by crises, such as recessions or pandemics, or a shift in research priorities or any disruptions in the research ecosystem. The growth in the latter years of the period under study can be attributed to the expansion of interdisciplinary research, collaboration levels and adoption of open science practices, amongst many other factors that have a bearing on research productivity levels.

By assessing the degree of collaboration, we could see that the collaboration levels were low, as researchers worked independently or with smaller research groups as compared to the latter half of the period under study. This could be due to factors not limited to a lack of communication or networking tools or practices that emphasize individual contribution. The noticeable increase in collaboration over the years could result from forged partnerships that were based on the pooling of knowledge and resources, leading to collaborative research outcomes. It could be fathomed that the research community from the G20 countries studying the field of Corporate Communication has embraced collaboration as an avenue to foster innovation, enhance research quality, and address research queries.

The keyword co-occurrence enabled us to analyse and visualise the relationships between the keywords

within the body of literature. This can be very useful for the exploration of interdisciplinary connections and cross-fertilisation of ideas. The keywords “Corporate Communication” and “Corporate Communications” were most frequently used. The scatter plots of the h and g index for authors and journals demonstrate interesting relationships between the variables. In both cases, there is a positive linear relationship, wherein, as the h-index increases, so does the g-index, implying a high frequency of collectively maximally cite publications and a broader impact on the author’s work. Our hypothesis that a significant correlation exists between the h and g index of authors and journals is accepted.

Through time series analysis, we gained valuable insights into future trends and patterns of research output from G20 countries in the Corporate Communication field. We could estimate 91 publications in 2028, 96 publications in 2030, 124 publications in 2040 and 151 publications in 2050 related to Corporate Communication. However, as time series analysis is based on historical data and assumptions, future outcomes may be influenced by factors beyond these. Factors like funding availability, policy changes, technological advancements, research priorities shift could significantly impact the publication trends. Nonetheless, the projections estimated mathematically, will provide the researchers, policymakers and institutions valuable information for strategic planning, resource allocation and understanding of potential growth or shifts in research output over time.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the findings that we have entered the watershed years of research output from G20 countries in the field of corporate communication. The study systematically gauged cumulative trends and publication levels, which will be useful for future planning and resource allocation in the field of corporate communication. It enabled tracking research progress and evaluating productivity and gaining insights into impact and dynamics of scientific community. We could gain a comprehensive picture of performance indicators like g-index, h-index, citations, productive authors, journals, degree of collaboration and make estimations for future research productivity.

The research approach is evolving and with higher levels of collaborations amongst researchers, we have access to a greater number of publications that are impactful. This scientometric study of publications contributed to a broader field of research evaluation and highlights the importance of scientometric analysis in understanding productivity

and its implications for advancing knowledge and addressing research queries.

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